

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Online service and accompanying report on the use of citizen information from smartphone apps for rapid earthquake detection and location estimation (EEW) – (Joint Deliverable with RISE project)

TURNkey

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Participant	Name	Country
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DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
CsLoc	Crowdsourced Seismic Location
iLoc	event location algorithm used in CsLoc
HMB	HttpMsgBus
TED	Twitter Earthquake Detection
EQN	Earthquake Network project

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1 INTRODUCTION

Rapid public earthquake information is essential for both the public and authorities and can contribute to a more efficient earthquake response (*Kanamori et al., 1997*). Until now, the majority of efforts to tackle this challenge have been oriented toward the implementation of dense seismological networks with fast and robust data communication. In the best cases, early warning systems have been deployed to rapidly locate earthquakes and estimate their magnitude using the closest seismic stations and potentially warn the population before the seismic waves reached their location (*Allen et al. 2009; Minson et al., 2018; Satriano et al, 2008*). However, those performant systems require high investment and maintenance, and therefore, they are only implemented in a few regions of the world. For many earthquakes worldwide, even a location within several tens of seconds of an event would be a useful acceleration of current practice.

EMSC has developed a system call CsLoc (Crowdsourced Seismic Location) (*Steed et al., 2019*) for the detection of felt earthquakes via crowdsourcing, which is capable determine fast and reliable seismic locations with only few seismic stations.

CsLoc methodology has been significantly improved since the start of the TURNkey project, over 3 main aspects. Because the same earthquake can lead to several crowdsourced detections (Twitter, the app, website, and recently EQN, in several countries), we have to determine on the fly that these detections are related to the same earthquake. It is very essential to avoid duplication of event in a fully automatic service (*Bondar et al., 2020*). The second improvement concerns the determination of the magnitude and thirdly, detections from an Earthquake Network Application (*Finazzi, 2016*).

Finally, beyond the method, CsLoc is becoming a service. All methodology were developed and tested using GEOFON network (*GEOFON data center, 2018*) which is a virtual network with contributions from many different agencies and institutions but are now implemented on a global virtual network offering an improved geographical coverage and results are now automatically published in the “[For Seismologist](#)” of the EMSC website¹ under the name CSLC.

This report will present CsLoc methodology and its latest improvements and then the performance evaluation based on two months of data. The performance review will be updated in June 2021 in a joint RISE/TURNkey report.

¹ <https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/seismologist.php?view=1>

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 CsLoc

While other crowdsourced approaches in seismology have focused on using accelerometers in smartphones (Cochran, 2018; Finazzi, 2016; Kong et al., 2016; Minson et al., 2015) or dedicated sensors that are maintained by the public (Cochran, 2018; Cochran et al., 2009), our approach is a side effect of the public's search for information or their online reactions. Presently, peaks in the rate of connections to the EMSC websites, LastQuake app launches, or tweets with certain keywords rapidly alert the EMSC that an earthquake is happening (Bossu et al., 2014; Bossu et al., 2018; Earle et al., 2011), with 85% of these crowdsourced detections having a known seismic cause. Multiple detections can sometimes occur because of the multiple detection methods and also since countries are monitored individually to increase signal-to-noise ratio. Following a detection, the barycenter of its activity is computed by applying a clustering algorithm to individual users' geolocations, which has been found to have an accuracy to within hundreds of kilometers of the earthquake's epicenter (see the Supplementary Materials in Steed et al., 2019). The barycenter represents a center of the public response and so is not necessarily expected to coincide with the epicenter; for instance, the earthquake could be offshore or in an uninhabited region. Hence, it indicates an earthquake's region but does not always provide an accurate estimation for its location. Nevertheless, this barycenter is the seed for the seismic location algorithm.

The CsLoc procedure is illustrated in **Figure 1**. Upon notification of a crowdsourced detection, CsLoc searches for phases from stations within 2000 km of the crowdsourced barycenter and close in time to the crowdsourced detection time. A "phase" or "arrival time" is the measured time that a seismic wavefront arrives at a seismic station. A simple phase association procedure is then used. The chosen phases are located in a window centered on a regression to the ak135 seismic propagation model (**Figure 2**) (Kennett et al., 1995). These phases are then analyzed by the location software iLoc (Bondár and Storchak, 2011). If a location is found, then the result must also satisfy publication criteria defined in terms of standard seismological parameters. Until the criteria are met, the process runs iteratively at 15-s intervals; each iteration may add newly received arrival times and starts from the solution obtained in the previous iteration. If people seem to react either to the P-wave or S-wave front, CsLoc collects only P-wave arrival times, which are provided by the GEOFON program from more than 800 stations affiliated to 73 seismic networks distributed worldwide from the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN) (GEOFON Data Center, 2018) and by a SeisComp3 server, held at EMSC. In near real time, data are received via the httpmsgbus (HMB) protocol (Heinloo, 2016), which is essential for the system's response time. The transmission of data from GEOFON to the EMSC has been measured to take less than 1 s. More details and analysis in Steed et al., 2019 and Bondár et al., 2020.

Figure 1: CsLoc fuses crowdsourced and seismic detection of earthquakes. Crowdsourced detections are quick but do not yield the physical properties of an event, and some detections are not related to seismic events. Seismic networks need strong quality criteria for the automatic publication of seismic events to avoid false detections. The fusion of the two sources of data improves the reliability of crowdsourced detections and reduces the response time of a seismic network for the rapid location of felt events.

Figure 2: The CsLoc association and location cycle, for iterations (A) 0, (B) 1, and (C) 2. Top row: The initial crowdsourced trigger (yellow circle) may be far away from the EMSC seismic location (green circle), but iLoc (red circle) converges fast to the traditional seismic location. Yellow, blue and green triangles show the seismic stations considered, associated and used in the locations, respectively. Bottom row: First-arriving P phase picks are considered in a time window (green lines) before the crowdsourced trigger. Those within three times the median absolute deviation (MAD) (blue lines and blue diamonds) of the best fitting travel time curve (red line) with the slope of the $ak135$ Pn velocity, 8.04 km/s, are passed to iLoc.

2.2 Crowdsourced detections

Crowdsourced detections are based on the immediate reactions of citizens to felt earthquakes on social media platforms and can therefore be used as an initial estimate of the earthquake location. CsLoc can be triggered by four Crowdsourced detections:

- the detection of a traffic peak at EMSC website: www.emsc-csem.org (Bossu et al., 2014);
- the detection of increased number of app launches of the EMSC's Lastquake app (Bossu et al., 2018);
- TED system (Earle et al., 2011), which is based on the detection of peaks in the rate of tweets with less than 7 words and containing the word "earthquake" in 59 languages;
- EQN detection (Finazzi, 2016), which is based on accelerometers in smartphones. The detection is based on a software at the central server that declares an earthquake when the number of smartphones reporting shaking during the past 30 s exceeds a threshold based on the expected number of reports in the absence of shaking due to earthquake waves.

Both TED and EQN are used at EMSC to publish a banner on the app and the website "potentially felt EQ, please confirm".

2.3 Multiple detection identification

A single earthquake can have multiple crowdsourced detections from each of the systems, as well as from neighboring countries within the same system. **Figure 3** shows examples in three different countries of CsLoc event location trajectories, starting from several different crowdsourced detections. Green trajectories denote web-based triggers, red lines LastQuake app triggers and blue ones TED triggers. One of the major strengths of our method is that regardless of the trigger type and the initial mislocation, CsLoc is capable to obtain a final solution that is very compatible to the final EMSC solution of the event.

Figure 3: Multiple strains for the same event (star) triggered by various country-based website traffic (green triangle) and TED triggers (blue triangle), as well as the LastQuake app (red triangle) crowdsourced detections in (A) Turkey, (B) Great Britain, and (C) Haiti. Corresponding color lines show the trajectory of CsLoc locations during the iterations. CsLoc shows a robust performance against the position of the initial crowdsourced triggers.

To deal with multiple triggers, we apply the Bondár et al., (2020) criteria, to determine if 2 crowdsourced detections are generated by the same event. We found that events with a large number of seismic arrivals

require separate logic from those with only few seismic arrivals. We rely on the assumption that if two solutions share a fair amount of common seismic arrival picks then the events are likely to be the same. For candidate events for multiple triggers we check the number of common seismic arrivals for each event pair. If the number of common seismic arrival picks is larger than 20, we declare the two events as common. For events with just a few picks, we require at least three common seismic arrival picks and that 20% of the seismic phases be shared between the events to declare them the same.

We publish the first location obtained by CsLoc, whatever the type of trigger and country, and because the magnitude is often obtained after more iteration, we only update the first location when a magnitude is available.

2.4 Magnitude estimation

Previous CsLoc studies (Steed et al, 2018; Bondár et al, 2019) focus on the speed and accuracy of the seismic locations. CsLoc is based on the iLoc (Bondár and Storchak, 2011; Bondár et al., 2018) location algorithm to locate the event and estimate the magnitude. To estimate the magnitude, GEOFON and the EMSC send automatic amplitude measurements along with the first P arrival picks processed by SeisComP via HMB (Heinloo, 2016). Currently, amplitude measurements for Local magnitude calculated on the vertical component **ML_v**, the narrow band body wave magnitude **mb** and Broad band body wave magnitude **mB** are received, even though the mb amplitudes are not used. Since we collect phase picks up to 1000 km (for sparse networks up to 2000 km) this would allow us to calculate mainly the local magnitude **ML_v** and in some rare cases the mB magnitude. Of course the **ML_v** magnitude starts to saturate relatively early at medium moment magnitudes, therefore for some cases ML would be an underestimated magnitude. For these events we will not publish ML at all.

2.5 Seismic station network

In Steed et al. (2018) and Bondár et al. (2019) studies, only seismic stations provided by the GEOFON program have been used. Although lots of seismic stations are already used, we added new seismic stations to fill up the gap in the GEOFON network. These new seismic stations are processed on by a SeisComP server operating at EMSC. All picks and amplitudes are sent to CsLoc on the fly via the HMB protocol (Heinloo, 2016).

Steed et al. (2019) study show that almost all non-located earthquakes are outside of the seismic stations network. To enhance the coverage, 362 seismic stations have been added from 92 networks. As CsLoc performs in the first 5 minutes of an origin time, it needs an extremely dense network around the crowdsourced detections to locate the earthquake.

Figure 4: Seismic station distributions. A: stations available for Steed et al. (2018) and Bondár et al. (2019) studies. B: Stations added for the TURNkey project and processed by the EMSC SeisComp. The GEOFON Network is a virtual network with contributions from many different agencies and institutions.

3 PERFORMANCES EVALUATION

CsLoc needs a good seismic stations coverage around crowdsource location to locate an earthquake, especially for small magnitude events which need very close seismic stations. Steed et al. (2019) and Bondár et al. (2020) studies have used restricted seismic stations in Indonesia. As CsLoc is now a public service, we can no longer use these stations which can induce a decrease in efficiency of CsLoc in this area.

The evaluation of performances is based on 378 felt earthquakes seen by crowdsourced detections recorded between September the 3rd 2020 and November the 16th 2020 at the EMSC (**Figure 5**). As one earthquake can lead to several crowdsourced detections, these 378 earthquakes correspond to 512 crowdsourced detections (**Figure 6 A**). There has been a number of fake crowdsourced detections, mainly from TED, none of them led to the creation of a fake seismic event. Among these 378 earthquakes, 139 have been located by CsLoc and 116 out of the 139 had also magnitude estimation.

Figure 5: Results of CsLoc analyses overlaid on a density plot of the number of seismic stations within 1000 km of each position. Successful locations are related to local network density: Almost all non-located events are out of the network.

Figure 5 shows that our earthquake dataset is not homogeneously distributed. They mostly occur in Chile and in the Dodecanese Islands as well as in the Balkan region. Most of the non-located earthquakes lay outside the network.

CsLoc is based on the location algorithm iLoc (Bondár and Storchak, 2011). **Figure 6 (B)** represents the result of CsLoc for the 512 triggers. CsLoc needs at least 4 seismic stations to produce a reliable location. Insufficient data means that 4 or less seismic stations were available. When CsLoc location does not satisfy the publication criteria defined in terms of standard seismological parameters (Bondár et al., 2020) the solution is poorly located and not published.

Figure 6 (C) shows the trigger delay after origin time for the 512 triggers. EQN is particularly fast with a trigger delay median of 18 sec. Other systems are fast with a trigger median delay of 58, 71 and 80 sec respectively for TED, Lastquake and the website. To locate a seismic event 18 sec after origin time, one needs a high rate of seismic stations availability in close range.

Figure 6: (A): Number of crowdsourced detections by systems. Some Earthquakes were detected by multiple systems. (B): Results of CsLoc for 512 triggers. (C): trigger delay after origin time for the different 328 located crowdsourced detections. The red lines inside the box represent the median and the box is limited by the first and third quartile

Two reasons can explain the number of not located earthquakes are:

- The distribution of magnitudes of our earthquakes dataset (**Figure 7**). It includes lots of small magnitudes (<4) which, even with our seismic stations coverage, are proved to be difficult to locate. The smaller magnitude for a felt earthquake is a ML 0.6 event in Croatia!
- For larger magnitudes, better seismic station coverage is needed (**Figure 5**). Even though 362 seismic stations have been added since September, more stations are required.

Figure 7: Distribution of magnitude of the 378 earthquakes

From the 378 earthquakes, 139 distinct earthquakes have been located by CsLoc and published by the deduplication algorithm. No duplicate event has been published, indicating that the deduplication criteria are well tuned. The system needs to be tested on a longer period. Nevertheless, CsLoc publication is very fast and is often the first seismic message published on the “for seismologist” EMSC website section (**Figure 8**). The median publication delays for the CsLoc locations are 93 sec, while it is around 201 sec (3 min 20 sec) for the EMSC publication delay. The median publication delay is 82, 121, 88, 113 s for EQN, TED, LastQuake and website, respectively. The fastest solution published by CsLoc was 43 sec after origin time. 90% of the CsLoc locations were located at less than 50 km. Locations affected by uncertainties greater than 50 km do not seem to follow a specific of pattern in terms of number of stations (except that they all used less than 20 picks, but iLoc is able to find a solution with at least 4 stations), or in terms of magnitudes.

Figure 8: Publication delay after the origin time for the 141 events located by CsLoc. (A): Box-and-whisker plot of publication delay for each crowdsource trigger types (blue), all CsLoc locations and the EMSC. The red lines inside the box represent the median and the box is limited by the first and third quartile. (B): Histogram of CsLoc (blue) and EMSC (red) publication delay after the origin time in seconds.

As part of the TURNkey project, we have added the computation of the magnitude by CsLoc. CsLoc computes only ML and mB magnitudes and are compared to EMSC magnitudes which can be Mw, mb, and ML. 116 CsLoc located events out of the 139, were published with a magnitude. Based on our small earthquake dataset, CsLoc tends to overestimate the magnitude by 0.3 (**Figure 9**). The difference between the EMSC and CsLoc magnitudes does not depend on the event location (**Figure 10 A**), nor by earthquake magnitude (**Figure 10 B**). We will investigate other causes that could explain the magnitude overestimation.

Figure 9: Histogram of the deviation of CsLoc magnitude determinations from EMSC values.

Figure 10: (A): Spatial distribution of the (EMSC – CsLoc) magnitudes. (B): Comparison between CsLoc magnitude and EMSC magnitude.

CsLoc is now a service, and its seismic locations and magnitudes are published since October 16th, 2020 (Figure 11).

2020-11-18 08:27:46.0	14.88 N	93.32 W	27	M	3.8	M	OFFSHORE CHIAPAS, MEXICO	UNM
2020-11-18 08:26:50.1	20.38 S	68.51 W	125	M	5.0	A	POTOSI, BOLIVIA	SC3
2020-11-18 08:26:48.0	20.31 S	69.14 W	104	ML	4.7	A	TARAPACA, CHILE	CSLC
2020-11-18 08:26:47.0	20.31 S	69.02 W	106	M	4.6	A	TARAPACA, CHILE	GFZ
2020-11-18 08:26:46.6	20.32 S	69.08 W	102	mb	4.8	M	TARAPACA, CHILE	NEIC
2020-11-18 08:26:46.1	20.33 S	68.96 W	108	mb	4.8	M+	TARAPACA, CHILE	INFO
2020-11-18 08:26:27.1	20.46 S	70.00 W	10	mb	4.8	M	TARAPACA, CHILE	RSBR
2020-11-18 08:23:03.0	5.07 N	125.52 E	170	M	3.2	M	MINDANAO, PHILIPPINES	PIVS

Figure 11: CsLoc seismic locations are published on the EMSC website in the For Seismologist section. The full message with the datetime of publication is available inside the CsLoc message.

4 CONCLUSION

CsLoc methodology has been significantly improved since the start of the TURNkey project over three main aspects. First, an algorithm to detect multiple crowdsourced detections generated by the same event has been implemented. Second, EQN detections have been added and third, and the computation of the magnitude has been implemented. 362 seismic stations have been added to collect picks-arrival times and amplitudes to increase our seismic network coverage. More seismic stations will be added in December 2020.

Our evaluation of performance is based on 378 felt earthquakes seen by crowdsourced detections recorded between September the 3rd 2020 and November the 16th 2020 at the EMSC which correspond to 512 crowdsourced detections. Our earthquake dataset is not homogeneously distributed and included lots of small earthquake ($M < 4$) generated by the Dodecanese Islands sequence and several small earthquakes ($M < 2$) in the Balkan region. The performance review will be updated in June 2021 in a joint RISE/TURNkey report. One can expect to have more than 1000 of felt earthquakes, which should allow us to have a more representative earthquake distribution in terms of magnitudes and locations.

CsLoc failed to find a solution for 286 out of 512 crowdsourced detections and 220 out of the 286 are due to a lack of seismic data (< 4 seismic stations). This, clearly, shows the need of increasing the number of seismic stations in some regions. A dedicated SeisComp server will be setup in December 2020 that will be in charge only for the picks and amplitudes processing.

EQN detections, added for the TURNkey project, are very fast with a trigger delay median of 18 sec which is almost 40 sec faster than twitter detections. Our study shows that Lastquake and the website are the most used source of crowdsourced detections.

The deduplication algorithm detects if 2 or more crowdsourced detections are related to the same event on the fly, in order to avoid the publication of the same earthquake several times. No fake seismic event has been published and 139 distinct earthquakes have been published since September 3rd 2020. 116 out of 139 were published with a magnitude. CsLoc computes only ML and mB magnitudes and seems to overestimate the magnitude when compared to EMSC magnitudes. More investigation needs to be performed and particularly on the instrumental response of the seismic stations.

CsLoc locations and magnitudes are published on EMSC website since October 16th 2020 (Deliverable D3.7).

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